

MMK: ACE
SMT.MITHIBAI MOTIRAM KUNDNANI:
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STUDENT'S SPECIAL ISSUE

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(PRINCIPAL)

Dr. AASHISH S. JANI
(EXECUTIVE-EDITOR)

FROM THE DESK OF THE EDITOR...!

After Covid-19 the education world has been changing very fast with drastic major changes in the research dimensions. UGC and MHRD have launched many virtual platforms with online depositories, e-books and other online teaching/learning materials. Combination of the traditional technologies' with mobile/web technologies to a single platform with depositories would enhance better accessibility and flexibility to education.

The main objectives of NEP 2020 clearly define the pivotal role in catalysing interdisciplinary /multi-disciplinary research culture at UG level.

Students' research at undergraduate and post graduate level is the key to success towards real life education. Implementation of this student centric research requires establishment of the Academic Bank of Credits (ABC), a national level facility which will be a bank for academic purposes with students as academic account holders. A minimum of 20 credits of the 160 credits in four years undergraduate degree programmes will be earned via research activities according to guidelines prepared under NEP 2020.

Further, it will encourage and make it possible for all students to open an academic bank account to commute credits to award any degree/research fellowship/certificates.

The ability to integrate classroom knowledge with practical problems is important to decide research problems of the real world and to provide realistic solutions for the same. Four years Undergraduate bachelor's degree programme objectives are clearly defined in these directions. This calls for developing research experiences in students and developing system of offering real life research projects with keen interest towards pursuing realistic research projects. Here role of research organisations, higher institutions or research centre can support research internships as providers.

Keeping such ideas in mind, I feel humbled to bring out the Third students special Issue of our reputed E-Journal "MMK: ACE", including research papers for the first time from students' community at various undergraduate, post graduate and Doctoral level Programmes of our College. This volume develops the fact finding empirical approach among students community at higher education.

I extend my sincere gratitude to the Management of H.S.N.C. Board and our respected Principal Prof. Dr. CA Kishore Peshori for their constant support and motivation towards a strong Research foundation.

Finally, a big thank you to the Peer-reviewers and Publishing House for helping us in publishing this E-Journal. I invite feedback and suggestions from our Readers, Researchers and Academicians for further improvement in our E-Journal "MMK: ACE".

Dr. Aashish S. Jani
Vice-Principal & Executive Editor

PRINCIPAL'S MESSAGE...!

Dear Members of the Academia,

It brings me immense joy and pride to witness the continued growth of SMT. M.M.K. College, especially in the realm of research, as evidenced by the expansion of our esteemed Research Centre in Commerce (Business Policy & Administration) and the recent approval in Accountancy.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to the dynamic editorial team, led by Dr. Aashish Jani, Vice Principal, for their unwavering commitment and dedication to advancing the cause of research at our institution. Their tireless efforts have played a pivotal role in steering our academic community toward the frontiers of knowledge.

In the spirit of our rich cultural heritage, I am pleased to include a Sanskrit shloka in this research endeavour, symbolizing the fusion of tradition and progress in our scholarly pursuits:

“चरैवेतिचरैवेति...”

“Keep Walking, Keep Walking”,

The present focus on student-centric research in this Third edition of MMK: ACE is indeed a commendable initiative taken at the opportune moment. It reflects our collective commitment to nurturing the research acumen of our students, a vital aspect of our academic mission.

I express my sincere appreciation to the Research Committee, whose proactive approach has not only fostered the development of new faculty but has also provided a platform for meaningful research at both undergraduate and postgraduate levels. The previous volumes of MMK: ACE have been well-received by the academic community, and I am confident that this edition, emphasizing student research, will further elevate our standing.

Kudos to the editorial team for curating diverse themes that delve into various facets of the Economy and Education sector. I extend my appreciation to the Course Coordinators, specialized students, academicians, research guides, and scholars whose valuable contributions have enriched the content of this journal.

I applaud the continuous efforts of the editorial board in cultivating and promoting a robust Research Culture across all multidisciplinary programs. Your dedication is instrumental in inspiring our faculty and students to embrace the role of researchers and critical thinkers.

As we embark on this intellectual journey through the pages of MMK: ACE, I wish the entire team the very best. May the ideas shared in this volume pave the way for positive outcomes and catalyze many more students and teachers to embark on the rewarding path of research and scholarly exploration.

With warm regards,

Prof. Dr. CA Kishore Peshori
(Principal)

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A Comparison of the Effectiveness of Learning in the Physical Classroom Versus Online Learning for Students during the COVID-19 Pandemic

MMK:ACE VOLUME 3:PAPER NO.05

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Abstract:- Teaching technologies have a wide spectrum of uses for learning processes, which have been expanded by the use of online educational resources and their impact on higher education. Currently, there has been more discussion of the utility of ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) in the teaching-learning process; unlike distance learning, these new tools are put to use through technologies. The current approach to social development, which is supported by innovation, learning, and research, is undeniable. Student satisfaction with blended e-learning has been studied within this framework. However, in distance university models supported by virtual platforms, we must ask ourselves whether students are satisfied when they are not in a face-to-face classroom environment. With the rapid and ongoing technological advancements, the education sector is undergoing a paradigm shift. Online, offline, and blended learning continue to evolve over time. The benefits, challenges, and requirements for teaching classes online, on the internet, and through blended learning methods are discussed. Suggestions for improving teaching and learning based on survey findings assist faculty members in planning teaching methodologies to meet the needs of students.

This study is based on a literature review, primary data, and secondary data sources. Secondary data was collected from the Official Website, as well as journals, exploration papers, and review papers, all of which were discussed during the study.

Keywords:- Online teaching, Blended learning, Offline learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching technologies have a wide spectrum of uses for learning processes, which have been expanded by the use of online educational resources and their impact on higher education. Currently, there has been more discussion of the utility of ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) in the teaching-learning process; unlike distance learning, these new tools are put to use through technologies. The current approach to social development,

which is supported by innovation, learning, and research, is undeniable. Student satisfaction with blended e-learning has been studied within this framework. However, in distance university models supported by virtual platforms, we must ask ourselves whether students are satisfied when they are not in a face-to-face classroom environment. With the rapid and ongoing technological advancements, the education sector is undergoing a paradigm shift. Online, offline, and blended learning continue to evolve over time. The benefits, challenges, and requirements for teaching classes online, on the internet, and through blended learning methods are discussed. Suggestions for improving teaching and learning based on survey findings assist faculty members in planning teaching methodologies to meet the needs of students.

Learning is an ever-changing phenomenon that has evolved over time. The effectiveness of learning is determined by the methodology used. The methodology or pedagogy is determined by the skillsets that students are expected to acquire. The COVID-19 pandemic provided an opportunity to test and evaluate various online teaching and evaluation tools. Students, teachers, and institutional administrators are the stakeholders in this case. Chang et al. had compared physical classroom learning efficacy to online learning efficacy in order to assess and improve learning quality. Students were polled on both methods of learning, and the results revealed that the learning efficacy of online class learning was higher than that of physical classroom learning. On the contrary, survey results indicated that physical classroom evaluation was more appropriate and fair than online examination. Students from various schools reported that their learning experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic period were effective and engaging. Singh et al. study emphasized the importance of developing appropriate infrastructure and capacity to support hybrid and blended learning methods. The faculty members were also introduced to various online learning methods and e-Learning tools as part of the capacity-building process. According to Singh et al. study, both learners and teachers should use innovative technology to enable effective teaching and engaged learning.

In contrast, blended learning combines in-person instruction with online learning methods. As a result, students can listen to a lecture in class and then take an online quiz right there or at home.

Consider a hybrid car and a blender. The same way that a hybrid car combines two types of fuel, hybrid learning combines two types of learning environments. Similarly to how a blender mixes whatever you put in it, blended learning combines various types of learning content.

A. *Benefits of Blended Learning:*

- Safer learning environment: If 2020 taught us anything, it's that being in one place with a bunch of other people can be complicated. And only seeing those people on the screen is excruciating. The blended approach makes learning safer by reducing the number of hours learners spend offline together while still allowing for live communication.
- Interactive learning process: Theoretical materials can be difficult to understand (if not boring). It's one thing for students to sit and listen to a speaker for several hours. And it's vastly different when they learn the same information by clicking on buttons, engaging in a dialogue simulation, enrolling in a game-like course, and so on. Learning new things can be enjoyable, and blended learning provides many tools to make it so.
- Learner Autonomy: Controlling and scheduling an individual learning path is critical for learners, especially adults. Learning isn't the only (or even the most important) activity that students and employees engage in. Work, family, hobbies, and friends are all important parts of people's lives, and learning should not be one of them. Learners in blended learning can access courses whenever they want and have the opportunity.

B. *Blended Learning Models:*

- Face-to-face driver model
- Online driver model
- Rotation model
- Flipped classroom
- Flex model

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To study an innovative teaching style.
- To analyse the online methods of teaching approach
- To understand the comparison of the effectiveness of learning in the physical classroom versus online learning for students.

III. RESEARCH PROBLEM OF THE STUDY

- A lack of understanding about incorporating digital tools into the teaching method.
- Some educational institutions have an inadequate infrastructure.
- Difficulty in incorporating innovative teaching methods into traditional teaching methods.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to (Foo, 2021)> Innovative educational adaptations have been essential during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, further evaluation before permanent adoption is warranted. A direct transition from the conventional way of teaching into an online-based format may not have the same impact. The time needed for students and tutors to become familiar with the new 'environment' should have been minimal. Technical issues such as Internet connectivity and lag time did not seem to be major problems in this locality. The fact that lower performance was also observed at the third tutorial suggested there was more than a transitional issue.

Effectiveness of Classroom and Online Learning: The effectiveness of online and classroom learning was evaluated using course content, pedagogical approaches, lesson interactivity and assessment, feedback, and evaluation.

Online Learning and Classroom Learning: Online learning has emerged as a topic of discussion in the twenty-first century. Online learning is the delivery of instruction through the use of digital resources. Electronic devices are used to deliver this type of learning. Online learning is also known as distance education, computerised electronic learning, and internet learning. With the introduction of online learning, students can now access their learning materials from anywhere and at any time. Over the last two decades, the advancement of technology has made education more accessible at all levels. According to (Hurlbut, 2018) & (Finger, 2007) As a result of technological advancement, the development of e-learning management systems and web resources has transformed online education by increasing the rate at which information can be disseminated and digested. Videos and live broadcasting play an important role in recent online learning trends.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is quantitative. This research supports a qualitative approach which enables the researcher to collect the information by allowing a study of issues and there by following a less structured format. The research work is completely based on secondary data which was collected from various sources from official websites, journals, research papers, books, and scholarly articles discussed during the study. The study is limited to a specific time and scope.

VI. CONCLUSION

Learning in any mode is dependent on the learner's thirst for knowledge, the instructor's ability to impart that knowledge, and both the learner's and the instructor's competency. Several online tools aided the teaching-learning process during the pandemic. Everyone recognized the importance of student-teacher-peer interactions during offline classes. The following conclusions have been reached to improve the current teaching-learning process.

- Because student-teacher-peer interactions are better in offline classes, they are preferred over online classes.
- Classroom learning combined with reading materials, PPTs, and videos shared with students by subject teachers allow students to learn outside of the classroom.
- Collaborative online tools, in addition to face-to-face discussions, are preferred for problem-solving.
- The majority of students prefer to learn from video lectures delivered by the same teachers who handle the subjects for theory and laboratory experiments.
- Many students prefer to express themselves during interactive sessions in class or during group discussions.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Chang, J. Y.-F. (2021). Comparison of learning effectiveness between physical classroom and online learning for dental education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal Dental Science*.
- [2]. Dr.M.Vaanmalar. (February:2021). A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN OFFLINE AND ONLINE CLASSES FOR STUDENTS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*.
- [3]. Finger, G. M. (2007). Information Security and Ethics: Tools, and Applications Information Science Reference. *Technol. Divers. High. Educ. New Challenges, Vol. I, 81-103*.
- [4]. Foo, C.-c. (2021). A comparative study regarding distance learning and the conventional face-to-face approach conducted problem-based learning tutorial during the COVID-19 pandemic. <https://bmcmededuc.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12909-021-02575-1>.
- [5]. Hurlbut, A. (2018). Online vs. Traditional Learning in Teacher Education: A Comparison of Student Progress Comparison of Student Progress. *American Journal of Distance Education, 32, 248-266*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08923647.2018.1509265>.
- [6]. Sharma, D. (2022). A Study on the Online-Offline and Blended Learning Methods. *J. Inst. Eng. India Ser. B (August 2022) 103(4):1373–1382*.